

A NEW TECHNIQUE FOR PREVENTION OF FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, a new technique to prevent free-edge delamination in composite laminates is presented. It is a series of short parallel slits cut along free-edge of the laminates normal to its loading direction. The experimental investigation is done on three kinds of specimens with stacking sequence: $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/90]_S$, $[\pm 15/\pm 45]_S$ and $[\pm 45/\pm 15]_S$. Test results show that these short slits could effectively prevent or delay initiation of edge delamination. Specimens with this treatment may have their tensile strength raised by 30-40% and the fatigue life extended even by an order of magnitude. Numerical calculation by a 3-D isoparametric finite element model was carried out for the interlaminar stresses in the neighborhood of the free-edge. The calculated results do indicate that in the presence of these pre-cut slits, a stress free zone along the free edge and a compressive interlaminar normal stress zone at their tips are created.

INTRODUCTION

To most of composite laminates with free edges, delamination seems to be more vulnerable and interlaminar stresses are considered to be responsible for the pre-mature edge delamination leading to the ultimate failure. For years, many works had been done trying to prevent the edge delamination so as to fully develop the potentiality of the composites. To improve the interlaminar bonding strength including the betterment of material toughness is one approach.^{1,2} The second approach is to reduce the interlaminar stresses developed in the laminates.³ Most of the previous researches in literature are concentrated to the former. However, due to the complexity involved in the work, these efforts were not too successful.

In the present work, a new technique is suggested based on the concept of second approach. In an attempt to eliminate the interlaminar stresses in the vicinity of free edges, a series of short slits are cut along the free edges of a coupon specimen normal to the loading direction. This kind of specimen is referred as "fish-bone specimen". The experimental investigation was carried out in three kinds of layups: $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/90]_S$, $[\pm 45/\pm 15]_S$ and $[\pm 15/\pm 45]_S$ both with coupon specimens and fish-bone specimens. Static tensile test and tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted on both specimens so as to compare any improvement in strength and fatigue life and to observe the changes in delamination characteristics. A three dimensional isoparametric finite element model was employed to calculate the interlaminar stress in coupon specimen and fish-bone specimen for each layup to further confirm the effectiveness of this new technique.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in the present study was F-class Glass/Epoxy prepreg. The laminates of three stacking sequences investigated were: $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/90]_S$, $[\pm 45/\pm 15]_S$ and $[\pm 15/\pm 45]_S$. Panels were autoclave-cured according to the manufacturer's recommending procedure. The coupon specimens were then cut from the panels with gage length 130 mm and width 40 and 32 mm referred as D-specimen and S-specimen. Parallel slits with equal depth of 4 mm and uniform distance 5 mm apart were cut along two free edges on some D-specimens. Those specimens with edge slits are called "fish-bone specimen", denoted as F-specimens. Fig.1 gives the configurations of both coupon specimen and fish-bone specimen.

Static simple tension tests were conducted on a Shimatsu test machine. During loading, the DUNEGAN/ENDVCO acoustic emission analyzer was mounted to monitor counts rate of specimen. An X-Y plotter was attached to the Shimatsu machine to draw load-displacement and AE-displacement curves during loading. Displacement was measured by a differential transducer mounted on the specimen over a 50 mm gage length. The specimens are translucent so that one can observe the damage developed in the specimens with help of powerful lightsource by naked eyes. A red dye penetrant was put along the edge of specimens in order to show any delamination more clearly. Ultimate load was determined by the complete failure of the specimens.

Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted on a MTS-880 servohydraulic fatigue machine under computer control. Each type of specimens (that is D, F and S specimens) of each layup was tested at a frequency of 1 Hz with various maximum and minimum loading levels. The load cycle was sinusoidal.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

1. Test Results

Table 1 summarizes the mean ultimate stresses with the range of values as shown in Fig.2 obtained from five coupon specimens and five fishbone specimens for each laminate layup, respectively. The ultimate stresses are calculated by the following formulas:

$$\sigma_u = \begin{cases} L/(W \cdot T) & , \quad \text{for coupon specimen} \\ L/[(W-2D) \cdot T] & , \quad \text{for fish-bone specimen} \end{cases}$$

where L represents the ultimate load, T the thickness of specimen, W the width of specimen and D the depth of edge slits (see Fig.1).

Table 1 The ultimate stresses of each laminate (MPa)

layups	D-specimens	F-specimens
$[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/90]_S$	226.4	284.2
$[\pm 45/\pm 15]_S$	334.2	450.8
$[\pm 15/\pm 45]_S$	227.4	314.6

Tables 2 to 4 give the ultimate fatigue lifes of each laminate layup under various maximum and minimum loading levels from coupon specimens and fish-bone specimens, respectively.

2. Development of Damage in the Laminated Specimens

For the D or S specimens of $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/90]_S$ laminate, edge delamination was formed and grew in -30/90 interfaces typically shifting from one interface, through 90-deg ply cracks, to its symmetric counterpart. Under

Table 2 Fatigue life of $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/\overline{90}]_S$ laminate

load level		D-specimen	S-specimen	F-specimen
980-10780	N	1810	128	3196
980- 8820	N	2365	498	5545
980- 6860	N	----	9245	30030

Table 3 Fatigue life of $[\pm 15/\pm 45]_S$ laminate

load level		D-specimen	S-specimen	F-specimen
980-9800	N	293	0	2100
98-7840	N	8826	429	13516
98-5880	N	61891	2886	108309

Table 4 Fatigue life of $[\pm 45/\pm 15]_S$ laminate

load level		D-specimen	S-specimen	F-specimen
980-12740	N	817	0	3129

static tension, the visible edge delamination appeared at about 70% of ultimate load accompanied by a sudden increase in counts rate of AE as shown in Fig.3. During cyclic loading, the edge delamination occurred as loading cycles reaching 15-20% of ultimate life of the specimens. Due to limited space of the paper, damage model of coupon specimen with orther layups is omitted.

For the fish-bone specimens with any layup of laminate, no visible delamination were found during static loading. However, immediately before the complete fracture, a series of damage zones consisting of matrix cracks and local delaminations were formed around the tips of pre-cut slits. Fig.4 gives the load-displacement and AE-displacement curves of fish-bone specimen of $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/\overline{90}]_S$ laminate. During cyclic loading, the above mentioned small damage zones can be found only after half of the specimen life passed. As loading continued, the damage zones extended much more in the direction of the length of the specimen than across the width. In any case the growth rate was very low because it was difficult for delamination to go through the stress free zones between the parallel slits. Eventually, the small damage zones at tips of the slits joined together and formed the edge delamination on each side of the specimen spreading along the entire length of the specimen and then across the width. The whole process from the very beginning up to the coalescence of all the damage zones might take about 80% of the entire life of the specimen.

STRESS ANALYSIS

The interlaminar stresses in both conventional laminated coupon specimens and fish-bone specimens used in the experiment are calculated by the finite element method using the three-dimensional eight-node isoparametric element. The material properties of Glass/Epoxy used in the analysis were experimentally determined as follow

$$E_1 = 27.07 \text{ GPa}; \quad E_2 = 3.68 \text{ GPa}; \quad G_{12} = 1.76 \text{ GPa}; \quad \mu_{12} = 0.24.$$

In addition, we assume

$$E_3 = E_2; \quad \mu_{13} = \mu_{23} = \mu_{12}; \quad G_{13} = G_{23} = G_{12}.$$

The calculated results reveal the following interesting facts that affirm the present technique:

- A. The region between any two parallel slits are essentially free of stresses except a small zone around slit tip.
- B. There may exist some stress concentrations both for interlaminar stresses and intralaminar stresses at tip of the pre-cut slit. However the interlaminar normal stress turns to be compressive on the interfaces of the proposed fish-bone specimens, thus may effectively prevent any delamination to be formed.
- C. For the coupon specimen of $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/\overline{90}]_S$ laminate, the normal stress σ_z is the dominant interlaminar stress. For $[\pm 45/\pm 15]_S$ and $[\pm 15/\pm 45]_S$ laminate, the shearing stress τ_{xz} is the dominant.

Due to limited space of the paper, only the numerical results of $[\pm 30/\pm 30/90/90]_S$ laminate are given here. Fig.5 shows the through-thickness and through-width σ_z distributions near the edge of the laminated D-specimen. Fig.6 and 7 show the through-thickness and through-width σ_z distributions in the laminated fish-bone specimen. Fig.8 shows the intralaminar stress σ_x distribution along the width of the fish-bone specimen in the 30-deg ply.

CONCLUSIONS

- A. The parallel pre-cut slits along the edges of composite laminate could create a stress-free zone near the free edge, thus effectively preventing or delaying the initiation of edge delaminations that often cause premature failure of the conventional laminated test specimens or the laminated structures with free edges.
- B. The fish-bone specimen proposed in the paper may provide the true strength and fatigue life of the tested composite laminates. This is of practical importance in the design of the laminated composite structure.

REFERENCES

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig.5

Fig.6

Fig.7

Fig.8